

The background of the cover is a faded, sepia-toned image of a handwritten manuscript. The text is in an old Italian cursive script. On the right side, there is a detailed anatomical drawing of a human figure, possibly a torso or a seated figure, with various lines and shading. The overall appearance is that of an antique document.

UPDATING HERSTORY

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Cover: graphic reworking of a sheet from Van Dyck's Italian Sketchbook depicting Sofonisba Anguissola

THEORY AND CRITICISM OF LITERATURE AND ARTS

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CONTENTS

Foreword,

Carla Rossi, 6

La Biblioteca Femminile Italiana e l'edizione dei sonetti ritrovati di Giovanna Grisalda Bianchelli e Adriana Polissena

Carla Rossi, 7-17

Nuove informazioni d'archivio su copiste e miniatrici del monastero del Paradiso di Firenze

Carla Rossi, 18-26

Asja Lācis: a Room of One's Own and Trajectories of Nonbelonging

Janis Taurens, 27-45

Im Schatten von Käthe Kollwitz. Die Künstlerinnen Sella Hasse und Elisabeth Voigt

Anja Degner, 46-74

Růžena Zátková. Un'esperienza di ricerca

Marina Giorgini, 75-97

Expanding Herstory: Imaging and Imagining Edmonia Lewis' Roman Ateliers

Gloria Jane Bell, 98-118

A short note on the alleged death certificate of Plautilla Bricci

Andrew Pritchard, 119-120

The date of the meeting between Antoon Van Dyck and Sofonisba Anguissola in Palermo

Carla Rossi, 121-126

“Ma era così per tutti”. L'assenza femminile nelle decisioni editoriali della casa editrice Einaudi negli anni '60

Maurizio Rebaudengo, 127-144

A Study in Sketches. Gunta Stölzl's Early Years in Munich (1914-1919)

Mirjam Deckers, 145-168

A brief note on the alleged death certificate of Plautilla Bricci

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I owe the correct reading of the alleged death certificate of Plautilla Bricci to the philological expertise of Professor Carla Rossi.

Consuelo Lollobrigida has recently placed Bricci's death at the age of 89, in December 1705.¹ As Yuri Primarosa² noted, the death certificate published by Lollobrigida, concerning a "Domina Plautilla" resident in Trastevere, can hardly be related to the artist.

The interesting fact, in my opinion, is that neither Lollobrigida nor Primarosa were able to transcribe the act (FIG. 1), which only an expert philologist like Professor Rossi is actually able to read, transcribe and understand. Lollobrigida even misread the month of the act she published, which would instead be October and most certainly not December.

This is a clear example of how sometimes the hybris should be put aside for the sake of scientific truth. I am aware that, before we decided to publish my brief note in this journal, Professor Rossi informed Consuelo Lollobrigida of the correct reading of the document, receiving a haughty reply.

I therefore reproduce here the document as it was transcribed for me by Rossi.

Die 13 octobris 1705 Plautilla Domina quondam [...]. etatis suæ annor[um] 36 c[irca]t[er], in domo conducta a[pu]d Viam Sanctæ Margaritæ, in communionem Sanctæ Matris Ecclesiæ animam Deo reddidit ac f[ui]t antea sacramentis, cuius corpus sepultura est in Eccl[esia] Sancte Margaritæ.

Translation: Lady Plautilla, daughter of the late [*the father's name is missing from the certificate*], aged about 36 years, in communion with Holy Mother Church, and in front of the sacraments, has rendered her soul to God, in a rented house located near the street of Santa Margherita, and her body is buried in the Church of Santa Margherita.

¹ C. Lollobrigida, *Plautilla Bricci. Pictura et Architectura Celebris. L'architetrice del Barocco Romano*, Roma 2017, p. 133.

² Y. Primarosa, *Elpidio Benedetti (1609-1690). Committenza e relazioni artistiche di un agente del re di Francia nella Roma del Seicento*, Fondazione 1563 per l'Arte e la Cultura della Compagnia di San Paolo, 2018, p. 41.

FIG. 1, Death certificate of a certain Lady Plautilla, aged 36, transcribed in the parish registers of the church of Santa Margherita in Trastevere

Plautilla Bricci, born in 1616, was certainly not 36 years old in 1705.

Lollobrigida's arguments are completely unfounded, since she claims (I translate from Italian): «In the seventeenth century, the appellation 'Domina' was reserved only for women, not noble, who had distinguished themselves for some liberal activity».³

Actually, the designation 'Domina', which occurs in the vast majority of mortuary records from the Middle Ages to the 17th century, refers, quite simply, to married women. The painter and architect Plautilla never married.

The last documentary trace in which Plautilla Bricci is still alive is Benedetti's will, drawn up in September 1690: «Lascio alla chiesa di S. Luigi de' Francesi quel pezzetto della isola delle mie case nella strada di S. Francesco che non fu compreso nel censo vitalizio che feci con detta chiesa di tutta l'isola [...], volendo sperare che col motivo di questo legato e delle altre spese de' miglioramenti fatte nelle case dopo il contratto del censo vitalizio si compiaceranno andare con cortesia nel pretendere la pigione della casa che donai alla Signora Plautilla Bricci sua vita durante, potendosi contrapporre un capitale perpetuo con uno temporaneo in persona d'età assai avanzata».⁴

³ Lollobrigida, *Plautilla Bricci*, 2017, p. 133.

⁴ C. Benocci, *Villa Il Vascello*, Rome, 2007, p. 178.